

Laser Raman Spectrum and its Vibrational Studies on Selenium Dioxide Difluoride†

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Laser Raman spectrum of selenium dioxide difluoride has been recorded in the range 200–4 000 cm^{-1} . The vibrational assignments have been made for the selenium dioxide difluoride molecule and the vibrational analysis has been made.

DURING the study of molecules of symmetry type XY_2Z_2 belonging to the C_{2v} point group which are of interest to the spectroscopists and chemists, we have come across an interesting molecule SeO_2F_2 . The complete vibrational frequencies of SeO_2F_2 are assigned on the basis of laser Raman spectrum of the compound.

Experimental

The spectrum for the sample obtained from Scientific and Industrial Supplies Corporation, Bombay, was recorded in a Cary 82 grating spectrophotometer equipped with argon ion laser using 488 nm line of power 4 W in the region 50–2 000 cm^{-1} . The observed frequencies are given in Table 1. The frequencies of all sharp bands have an accuracy of $\pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE 1—LASER RAMAN FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF SELENIUM DIOXIDE DIFLUORIDE

Frequency*	Assignment
277w	$\nu_7 (a_2)$
285m	$\nu_4 (a_1)$
332m	$\nu_7 (b_1), a(b_2)$
356s	$\nu_3 (a_1)$
430w	$\nu_8 - \nu_4$
620vw	$\nu_4 - \nu_7$
704s(p)	$\nu_2 (a_1)$
760m	$\nu_6 (b_1)$
968s(p)	ν_1
1 059w	ν_6
1 320w	$\nu_1 + \nu_3$
1 408m	$2\nu_1$
1 938m	$2\nu_1$

*vw = very weak, w = weak, m = medium, s = strong, s(p) = strong (polarised).

Results and Discussion

Frequency assignment: SeO_2F_2 molecule belongs to C_{2v} symmetry with an approximate tetrahedral shape. As expected nine fundamental vibrations

appear in laser Raman spectrum. The polarised lines at 968 and 704 cm^{-1} are assigned to Se–O and Se–F symmetric stretches, respectively. The medium band at 760 cm^{-1} is assigned to Se–F asymmetric stretch while the weak band at 1 059 cm^{-1} is assigned to the Se–O asymmetric stretch. The torsional mode ν_8 is assigned to the weak line at 277 cm^{-1} . These conclusions have been arrived from the analogy with SO_2F_2 ¹. It may be noticed that there should be a difference of 15 cm^{-1} between ν_4 and ν_5 vibrations². From this observation, the band at 285 cm^{-1} is assigned to ν_4 . The strong Raman line at 356 cm^{-1} is assigned as ν_3 S–O bend in comparison with the allied molecules. The remaining band at 332 cm^{-1} is assigned to both ν_7 and ν_6 which have a very similar frequency in SO_2F_2 . The remaining frequencies are assigned to the various combinations and overtones of the nine fundamental frequencies.

Normal coordinate analysis: The structure and nomenclature of the parameters of the molecule under investigation is shown in Fig. 1. The

Fig. 1. Geometry, bond distances and bond angles of the XY_2Z_2 type molecule.

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normal coordinate analysis of selenium dioxide difluoride molecule has been carried out on the basis of C_{2v} point group following Wilson's F-G matrix method using a modified set of symmetry coordinates³. The molecular kinetic constants and a set of potential constants obtained are given in

 TABLE 2—VALUES OF KINETIC CONSTANTS (10^{-22} g) AND FORCE CONSTANTS (10^5 dyne cm^{-1})

	Kinetic constants	Valence force constants	Kinetic constants	Valence force constants
d	2.589 9	8.098 3	rr	0.094 5
dd	0.138 7	-0.037 6	rr'	-0.221 8
D	3.746 4	0.916 9	rr''	0.046 3
DD	0.986 7	0.847 6	dr	0.671 7
α	2.747 5	1.845 8	dr''	0.277 6
β	-0.161 7	0.974 9	d α	0.311 5
$\alpha\beta$	-0.420 7	-1.137 3	d β	0.300 3
βr	-0.681 3	-0.196 3	Dr	0.181 6
αr	0.002 6	0.000 7	Dr'	0.657 4
dD	0.689 7	0.257 1	D α	-2.409 9
r	0.752 5	0.265 5	D β	0.675 7
				-0.321 6

TABLE 3—MEAN AMPLITUDES AND CENTRIFUGAL DISTORSION CONSTANTS

	Vibrational mean amplitudes at 298.16 K 10^{-3} A	Centrifugal distortion constants kHz
$l_{\bar{d}}(X-Z)$	1.583 1	D_J 6.677 7
$l_{\bar{D}}(X-Z)$	1.722 0	D_{JK} 7.790 9
$l_{\bar{p}}(Y...Y)$	4.308 4	D_X -12.561 8
$l_{\bar{q}}(Z...Z)$	9.083 5	R_A -0.644 2
$l_{\bar{r}}(Y...Z)$	8.787 5	R_B -0.041 8
		J -0.897 6

TABLE 4—CORIOLIS COUPLING CONSTANTS

ζ^{μ}		ζ^{ν}	
ζ_{15}^{μ}	0.136 3	ζ_{38}^{ν}	0.315 6
ζ_{25}^{μ}	0.369 8	ζ_{45}^{ν}	-0.490 1
ζ_{35}^{μ}	0.918 6	ζ_{19}^{ν}	0.518 4
ζ_{45}^{μ}	-0.029 6	ζ_{29}^{ν}	0.562 7
ζ_{16}^{ν}	0.180 9	ζ_{39}^{ν}	0.607 4
ζ_{26}^{ν}	0.708 9	ζ_{49}^{ν}	0.607 4
ζ_{36}^{ν}	0.018 0	ζ_{56}^{ν}	-0.338 7
ζ_{46}^{ν}	0.641 5	ζ_{57}^{ν}	0.428 1
ζ_{17}^{ν}	0.316 3	ζ_{68}^{ν}	0.397 0
ζ_{27}^{ν}	0.507 7	ζ_{59}^{ν}	-0.579 7
ζ_{37}^{ν}	-0.227 4	ζ_{68}^{μ}	-0.214 1
ζ_{47}^{ν}	-0.768 5	ζ_{69}^{μ}	-0.519 0
ζ_{18}^{μ}	-0.251 3	ζ_{78}^{μ}	0.744 7
ζ_{28}^{μ}	0.772 7	ζ_{79}^{μ}	-0.303 2

Table 2. These individual constants have been used to evaluate mean amplitudes (Table 3), Coriolis coupling constants (Table 4) and centrifugal distortion constants (Table 3).

The force constants f_d is very much greater than f_b indicating that Se-O bond is stronger than Se-F bond. The values of kinetic constants, bonded and non-bonded vibrational mean amplitudes are in the expected range.

The zeta values obey the following quadratic sum rules,

$$\sum_{i,j} (\zeta^{\mu})^2 = 1 \quad (i = 1 \text{ to } 4, j = 8, 9)$$

$$\sum_{i,j} (\zeta^{\nu})^2 = 1 \quad (i = 1 \text{ to } 4, j = 8, 9)$$

$$\sum_{i,j} (\zeta^{\mu})^2 = 1 \quad (i = 1 \text{ to } 4, j = 5)$$

The high zeta values of ζ_{25}^{μ} , ζ_{26}^{ν} , ζ_{47}^{ν} , ζ_{78}^{μ} and ζ_{46}^{ν} show that the coupling between the vibrations concerned are significant.

 TABLE 5—HEAT CONSTANT, FREE, ENERGY AND HEAT CAPACITY ($cal K^{-1} mol^{-1}$) OF SELENIUM DIOXIDE DIFLUORIDE MOLECULE FOR THE IDEAL GASEOUS STATE OF 1 ATMOS. PRESSURE

T K	$\frac{H_0 - E_0^0}{T}$	$\frac{E_0 - E_0^0}{T}$	S^0	C_p^0
298.16	12.748 1	59.621 8	72.369 9	10.426 0
300	12.782 9	59.700 3	72.483 2	10.524 6
400	13.321 9	63.620 7	76.942 6	12.680 1
500	15.872 5	67.008 5	83.493 2	14.100 6
600	16.986 0	70.004 4	86.990 4	15.047 2
700	17.893 6	72.693 2	90.586 8	15.694 9
800	18.268 3	75.133 1	93.401 4	16.151 5
900	19.268 3	77.366 0	96.634 3	16.482 8
1000	19.797 5	79.424 3	99.221 8	16.729 7

The thermodynamic functions for selenium dioxide difluoride molecule have been calculated for the ideal gaseous state at one atmospheric pressure assuming a rigid rotor harmonic oscillator model. The influence of anharmonicity, non-rigidity and spin contribution are neglected. The values are presented in Table 5. These constants can be used for the interpretation of the experimental results on thermodynamic properties.

References

1. T. BIRCHALL and R. J. GILLESPIE, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 681.
2. D. R. LIDE, D. E. MANN and R. M. FRISTROM, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 26, 734.
3. S. MOHAN and T. J. BHOOPATHY, *Acta Phys. Hung.*, 1986, 60, 3.